

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF DIGITAL LINGUISTICS, ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND TEACHING METHODS IN EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845844>

Technology will never replace great teachers, but technology in the hands of great teachers is transformational. - **George Couros**

***Abstract.** This article explores the growing need and the influence of digital linguistics, artificial intelligence, and modern teaching methods in new alterations of education. Digital linguistics is considered as an essential part of today’s classroom teaching environment as it makes the lesson more interactive, engaging and helps with active learning the actual language that is in daily use. As digital tools develop, their offering assistance would grow with them, so they can analyze better, and allows learners to adjust them, taking into consideration their own needs in education. This endless adaptation strengthens the effectiveness of the new developing technologies and creates a bond between technologies and their users. It gives more insights to both teachers and students about the common mistakes that are made and might have been continuously overlooked in a matter of seconds, which helps them to work on that mistakes and become more confident in their skills of learning the language and for teaching it. Talking about artificial intelligence, it is more about getting a personalized feedback, plans, advice, guidance in the field of education and emotional support and instant process of data for the individual use, that is somehow related to the education as well. From small choices to making the crucial ones, AI always provides with unbiased advice and tips, proving its’ meaningful role in our lives. Finally, the article highlights how teaching methods have changed from traditional classrooms to the modern ones. How they have altered from being teacher-centered to being student-centered and the reasons why it is more efficient than the old methods that are used decades before. The combination of these three topics relation highlights the adaptability and the practicality of education, that is uniquely welcomed by both learners and educators.*

***Keywords:** teachers and students, learners and educators, help, in a matter of seconds, education.*

Introduction: Education has always been an important topic of discussions and has always been considered as the dynamic field, however, the changes that its’ facing in 21st century are more profound than it has ever been. With the evaluation of new technologies, the methods of teaching and learning are also evaluating. Once needed classrooms with huge textbooks are no longer appreciated and now their places are taken by the digital devices, with a class full of students who are eager to be part of an interactive, communication added lessons with creative teaching methods. As a result, three essential components – digital linguistics, artificial intelligence, and modern teaching methods have become the center of contemporary education. These factors change the way of education for both teachers and students, broadening their horizons, and changing the way of delivering information in a more modern way. These innovations need time to develop and constant adaptation, which might make educators to

rethink about the more effective ways of educating students and getting rid of traditional structures, as now they are considered as outdated and boring. New technologies help student to develop their critical thinking, creativity and adaptability, since the technologies themselves are creative, deep thinking and adaptable. All these alterations, illustrate how the education systems are moving fast and getting better day by day, by boosting the efficiency of personalization, accessibility and so many more things, that had not been prioritized before like it is now.

Main part: Digital linguistics plays a significant role in today’s world as it studies the usage of language, and the way of processing it in digital spaces. Rather than focusing on the use of computers for performing language-related tasks, such as: machine translation or voice recognition, sub-domains of Computational Linguistics, Digital Linguistics analyses, preserves and disseminates language data, i.e. digital artefacts that use language as a means of human expression. News articles, social media content, or digitized medieval manuscripts are all potential objects of interest for Digital Linguistics. Closely related to Digital Humanities, Digital Linguistics is attracting increasing attention from academic communities as well as the public and private sectors, since skills in handling digital language data are considered essential in the modern economy and society. Instead of only rely on textbooks, students are able to get to know how the language is actually used by natives in real life. This is more about practicing the language in an active way, which makes the learning path more effective and natural. Digital Linguistics are also very useful for teachers. It improves the method of teaching by creating better materials for teachers to use throughout the lesson. It might also help with detecting common mistakes that students make unconsciously and teachers can help them to overcome that specific problems by giving them personalized feedback. Additionally, the best part about using digital linguistics is that, they make the learning way more engaging and might ignite interest for students who aren’t interested in learning the subject. The ones that I believe as the most effectives would be grammar checkers, translators, pronunciation correcting based ones and definitely the assistant apps which are always ready to help with writing and idea providing for speaking. These programs help everyone who uses them to become more confident on the language that they are studying, makes a room for them to self-study and achieve independency. Thanks to their instant feedback, students now do not need to wait for their teachers to correct them or overthinking thousand times before asking a simple question. These system of education makes the process of learning more safe, accurate, convenient, modern and way more connected to the actually used language.

Moving on to the topic of AI, it is apparent that nowadays there is no single soul who is not aware of artificial intelligence. It already plays a crucial role in our lives; it helps us to choose between very basic things that we can opt for ourselves, yet still want it to decide for us, since it is more convenient. Such as: movie recommendations, which song to listen to next, which homework to do first, should we try a new thing or stick to the old habits and so much more. Also, it helps with more sophisticated choices that we have to opt for, that could change our entire life. As: deciding which university to apply, which job can highlight our true potential and skills, it also assists us to get rid of our bad habits with giving tips we had not known in years. AI is now helping to billions of people, to overcome stress, depression, anxiety and even encouraging them to move on from their childhood traumas, that had been taunting them for decades. It acts like a personal therapist that is unbiased, not judging, but only listening, understanding and being a good advisor that everybody needs in their lives. Obviously, there are

people who are wrapped on their own shelves and struggle with opening up to those who around them. For such people AI is the best option that they can look up for. Of course, there is a huge drawback, which is AI's incapability to show empathy, but at least, it can imitate that empathy and choose the right words to lift up the moods of people. Which is already a big thing and a giant help that is offered unconditionally. Although, I highlighted the examples of AI's role and importance in our personal lives above, I also must to mention its' role in broader functions. Artificial intelligence is now doing the things, that humans would spend months in doing, in a matter of seconds. It is making our lives easier, in every aspect possible. Taking an education as an example, I can confidently say that AI has transformed the traditional understanding of learning and teaching. It helps teachers analyze students' progress faster, identify the areas where they struggle the most, and provide more effective approaches to improve their performance. It helps students to plan a personalized schedule of their daily routine with effectively adding practices of the subject that they are passionately learning. It can also create a clear path of learning any skill with extra tips and with pieces of advice. Besides all, AI is able to explain difficult topics in the easiest way possible which makes the work of both teachers and students easier. In universities, AI supports scientific research by processing a huge amount of data that could take years of research, and could have created a stressful life for every educator and learner. Because of these reasons, AI is not only a convenient tool, but is becoming a true game-changer for both teaching and learning and for any other field that exists out there.

Switching off to the topic of Teaching Methods in education, it is clear that they had evolved significantly over time. Back then, traditional methods of teaching were more teacher-centered. Teachers would explain the topic, give examples, help students to do exercises and bring new ideas, so students would not get bored in their lessons. Besides, traditional teaching is used to be stricter, students needed to sit in one place, raise their hands if they wanted to ask anything and the pressure of the classroom made students even fear from asking questions. Unlike the modern teaching ways. Now, students are more responsible for the lesson to be engaging than teachers, they have to work more, do research on the new topic before teacher explains it, create unique exercises for their classmates, be more active in the class and show their understanding of the subject. They are now boosting their ability to think independently, to express their thoughts and creativity. Students are not intimidated of asking questions no more, which is making the classroom atmosphere more friendly and open than scary. It is also worth mentioning that, modern methods are more blended. They know exactly that sticking to the same method will not work, so they are using diverse methods on a single subject, which creates more flexible learning environment. Teachers are now free to add their own spice to lessens, compared to then when they had to follow the strict teaching plan that was made by the government for them. Indeed, they still have that teaching plans, but they also are welcomed to add or remove some parts of it, depending on the students they are teaching. Now teachers can conduct a lesson that would be understandable for every student, no matter of their level of that specific subject. That is why the progress of students nowadays are better than they used to be once. Creative methods like role-plays, road trips and simultaneous project performances can't be overlooked as well. They are making the classroom more engaging, making students move, rather than sitting in one spot, making them think different scenarios and is boosting their soft skills. These methods are more practical and the level of understanding of students are much higher when such methods are used in educating them, instead of just making them to learn everything by

heart. Even if they do learn everything by hard, they will forget it in a matter of time but the lessons, taught in a unique way would remain in their minds contemporary.

Conclusion: To be conclude, digital linguistics, artificial intelligence, and modern teaching methods make engaging, flexible and effective classroom environment no matter of if they are combined all together or not. They make the learning path more efficient, natural, relevant, and connected to the real life usage of the knowledge, since they offer a wide-range of data in a small amount of time, analyze of the work that you may be unsure of accuracy, and innovative unusual ideas that are welcomed by learners. Overall, their impact illustrates how having good time in education, with adding spice to the class brings more good than harm to the class environment. Besides, they make it clear the fact that technology only assists you to be more creative and independent thinker.

REFERENCES

1. Digital Linguistics article written by Vijaykumar Selvaraj and Sheik Hameed.N on the Journal of the Asiatic society; pages 40-41 on the journal, pages 1-2 on the article itself, September 2023 edition.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/373686782_Digital_Linguistics
2. Artificial intelligence in Education, on the Digital Promise website
3. https://digitalpromise.org/initiative/artificial-intelligence-in-education/?gad_source=1&gad_campaignid=20185001884&gbraid=0AAAAAppQu-ovxlmVRWb1SnFqBScDT_AAx&gclid=CjwKCAiAuIDJBhBoEiwAxhgyFIWsapTsMSlG3WAKyZDeP_ZcL22Te2nhw7GrsYW-gCVXfTEMBqjzbhoCeDYQAvD_BwE
4. The importance of AI in our daily life, Dr. Muhammad Adnan Khan \ 15 Jul 2024
5. <https://www.hu.ac.ae/knowledge-update/from-different-corners/the-importance-of-ai-in-our-daily-life>
6. Journal Graduate Programs for educators, the article “Teaching methods for the 21st Century” by Janelle Cox. First 3 and last 3 paragraphs are used.
7. <https://www.graduateprogram.org/blog/teaching-methods-for-the-21st-century/>
8. European school education platform (free courses) \ Title: Innovative teaching methods, strategies and approaches for teachers\01.09.2025 updated\ by Emilia-Romagna
9. <https://school-education.ec.europa.eu/en/learn/courses/innovative-teaching-methods-strategies-and-approaches-teachers-bologna>